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Revision of the Qualification Framework at the Technical University of Denmark

Part 1: Concepts

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ABSTRACT

When the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) adopted the National Qualification Framework (NQF), it was implemented as an add-on to the existing concept in place for describing educational outcomes, rather than by redesigning the educational outcomes themselves. The system in place does not emphasize the type and extent of knowledge, skills, and competencies adequately to facilitate programme development and evaluations. In this work, an expansion and reorganization of the qualification elements in the NQF at DTU is proposed as a means to facilitate a more detailed design and evaluation of the educational programmes. The top level categories of *knowledge*, *skills*, and *competencies* are reorganized into four categories: *-to know*, *-to be*, *-to interact*, and *-to do*. Knowledge of praxis is a new element in the category *-to know*. The new category, *-to be*, includes mind-set development and self-instruction. The category, *-to interact*, includes competencies in communication and teamwork. The category, *-to do*, includes operative skills and competencies in problem solving. Each of the four main categories contain a number of qualification elements. Suitable taxonomies are suggested for each of the main categories.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum development, Quality Assurance and Accreditation, Engineering Skills

Keywords: Qualification framework, educational outcomes, constructive alignment

INTRODUCTION

When the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) adopted the Danish National Qualifications Framework [1] (NQF), the new concept of *knowledge*, *skills*, and

competencies was implemented as an add-on to the existing set of qualifications. Each educational programme constructed a qualification matrix with the existing qualifications listed vertically and the NQF descriptors *knowledge*, *skills*, and *competencies* as the horizontal axis. However, the application of only three descriptors has proven to provide inadequate detail in all aspects of programme design, implementation and evaluation. In this paper, we propose a revision of the *knowledge*, *skills*, and *competencies* categories and present a number of taxonomies aimed at the different types of qualifications. In a companion paper [2], applications are demonstrated for three B. Sc. in Engineering programmes.

1 EXPANSION OF THE QUALIFICATION FRAMEWORK

The NQF organizes qualifications into three descriptors: knowledge, skills, and competencies. UNESCO [3] uses four descriptors: *to know*, *to be*, *to cooperate*, and *to do*. In this section, these approaches are combined to form a revised qualification framework.

1.1 Current framework

The current descriptors of the NQF for programmes at the Bachelor of Science (B. Sc.) level are listed in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Descriptors of the Danish National Qualification Framework [1]

Knowledge	1	Must have knowledge about theories, methods, and praxis within one or more disciplines or professions.
	2	Must be able to understand and reflect on theories, methods, and praxis.
Skills	3	Must be able to apply methods and tools associated with one or more disciplines and be able to apply general skills required by employees in a discipline or profession.
	4	Must be able to interpret theoretical and practical problems and apply relevant methods for analysis and problem-solving.
	5	Must be able to communicate the nature of problems and their solutions to peers as well as to non-specialists.
Competencies	6	Must be able to handle complex entrepreneurial challenges in study and work situations.
	7	Must be able to work independently and to cooperate in groups in a professional manner.
	8	Must be able to identify personal need of learning and to orchestrate self-instruction in different learning contexts.

The NQF contains eight educational levels with Bachelor of Science ranked 6, Master of Science ranked 7 and the Ph. D. as the eight and top level. In an indirect manner, the NQF thus represents a taxonomy for educational outcomes. The NQF does not offer a taxonomy for measuring progression in learning within each such level. This is one reason for developing a qualification framework aimed specifically at the B. Sc. in Engineering programme. Another reason is the absence of a clear distinction between skills and competencies. While descriptor number 3 fits the category of skills very well, descriptors number 4 and 5 are indistinguishable in nature from descriptors 6, 7, and 8. Descriptors number 4 and 6 are both about problem solving and could be merged into one descriptor. Placing descriptor number 5 about communication within the skills category is also questionable. Another accepted opinion is that mastery of languages is a skill, while communication of professional matters is a competency. Finally, the NQF fails to address the development of a personal and professional mind-set.

1.2 Revised framework

Besides rectifying shortcomings in the current NQF mentioned above, a revised framework must also facilitate constructive alignment by defining qualifications that are equally meaningful at the programme level and at the level of individual courses. A third objective of a revised framework is to facilitate a more systematic use of taxonomies as a linkage between programme outcomes and course outcomes.

Table 2 defines the top two levels of the revised qualification framework. The three major categories based on knowledge, skills, and competencies have been abandoned in favour of four categories similar to UNESCO's *Four pillars of learning* [3]. The first category, - *To know*, is essentially identical to the knowledge category in the NQF. The second category, - *To be*, is a new addition, emphasising development of a personal and professional mind-set. This category, by some referred to as the *Disciplinary future self* [4], includes the notion of *Life long learning*, which here has been renamed *Self-instruction* in order to strengthen its relevance in the minds of young students. The third category, - *To interact*, includes communication as well as teamwork, and is therefore similar to the notion "Learning to live together" in UNESCO's *Four pillars of learning*. The fourth category, - *To do*, is the combination of operative skills and problem solving. The most noticeable change in the organization of the revised qualification framework is the significant narrowing of the definition of skills and its closer association with problem solving. This closer association is motivated by the taxonomy for problem solving presented in the next section.

Table 2. Components of a revised qualification framework

1 st level	2 nd level descriptors	Description
1: - To know	Knowledge of theories	Acquire and apply terminology and facts, theories, laws of nature, methods, and procedures.
	Knowledge of praxis	Apply knowledge about praxis-induced boundary conditions and their influence on the applicability of theories and methods.
2: - To be	Mind-set	Develop a personal and professional mind-set.
	Self-instruction	Identify need for new knowledge, gather resources, execute, and evaluate learning outcomes.
3: - To interact	Teamwork	Conduct, coordinate, lead, monitor, and develop teamwork.
	Communication	Master language and tools, structure content, choose between narrative styles, edit for logic and clarity, and define communication objectives and receiver competencies.
4: - To do	Operative skills	Advance degree of training, from novice to expert, in executing manual and cognitive tasks.
	Problem solving	Interpret problem information, identify objective, diagnose problem, choose strategy, execute and evaluate solution, interpret impact of solution.

2 QUALIFICATION CATEGORIES AND THEIR TAXONOMIES

A qualification framework serves not only to define educational outcomes but also to construct an alignment between outcomes at the programme level and at the level of individual courses. A qualification framework must also take into consideration the learning processes facilitated by the courses and it becomes necessary to distinguish

between learning objectives and learning processes. The complexity of learning objectives and the complexity of learning processes cannot be described by a single taxonomy.

2.1 Object and process complexity

Academic complexity follows the scholarly advancement semester-by-semester from introductory courses to more advanced courses in the final year of a programme. We will refer to this dimension of complexity as *object complexity*. The complexity of the processes engaged in acquisition and use of knowledge is here referred to as *process complexity*. Bloom's taxonomy (*Figure 1*) for the cognitive domain [5] is one of the most used taxonomies for measuring process complexity.

Figure 1. Bloom's taxonomies for the cognitive [5] and affective domains [6]

Bloom's taxonomy for the cognitive domain only describes the process complexity in acquiring and using knowledge. This taxonomy is thus not suitable for defining the topic complexity of the individual courses within a program. To document progression in topic complexity from the beginning to the end of a programme, a course hierarchy scale is needed (see *Table 3*).

Table 3. Course level hierarchy

Course levels	Description	Characteristics
4. Capstone	Projects, capstone design, internships, and thesis work	Non-taught programme activity.
3. Discipline specialization	Intermediate level studies in sub discipline.	Elective course aimed at a subpopulation of students within a programme. Has <i>Discipline core</i> courses as its prerequisites.
2. Discipline core	Discipline specific foundation courses.	Unique to a specific programme. Has <i>Generic foundation</i> courses as its prerequisites.
1. Generic foundation	Discipline independent courses.	Shared between many programmes.

Courses at the *Generic foundation* level are introductory courses, often with no prerequisite courses, typically first-year courses in natural science. *Discipline core*

courses are first level engineering courses, which only have introductory natural science courses as their prerequisites. Such courses typically have little or no inter-dependencies. At the *Discipline specialization* level we place second level engineering courses, where each course may have several first level engineering courses as their prerequisites. A course in instrumentation typically embraces both analogue and digital electronics as well as programming and a course in biomaterials embraces cell biology and materials science. At the top of the course ranking, *Capstone courses* are project courses, capstone design courses, internships and thesis work.

2.2 –To know

The qualifications in the category, *–to know*, is founded on Krathwohl's elements of knowledge [5], but extended with *knowledge of praxis* (Table 4).

Table 4. Qualification elements of knowledge

Knowledge elements	Description
1.5 Metacognitive knowledge	Knowledge of cognition in general and awareness of one's own cognition.
1.4 Knowledge of praxis	Knowledge of praxis or regulatory induced limitations to application of theories, methods, and materials within relevant disciplines.
1.3 Procedural knowledge	Knowledge of procedures and methods and the criteria for their use.
1.2 Concepts	The interrelationships among the basic elements within a larger structure that enable them to function together.
1.1 Facts and terminology	The basic elements required to be acquainted with a discipline or to solve problems in it.

The elements of knowledge in Table 4 are organized from low to high level of complexity and should be considered to have cumulative dependencies. They form one axis in a *knowledge-qualification matrix* and the levels of Bloom's taxonomy for the cognitive domain forms the other axis. Thus, with respect to acquisition and use of knowledge, course instructors should not only aim high on Bloom's taxonomy for the cognitive domain but also aim high on the scale of knowledge elements (Table 4). Both scales in the *knowledge-qualification matrix* are independent of topic complexity, hence first semester courses should aim just as high as last semester courses.

2.3 –To be

The elements of mind-set development are divided into two major categories, personal mind-set and professional mind-set (Table 5).

Table 5. Qualification elements of mind-set

Mind-set	Components	Description
Professional mind-set	6. Product-oriented	Embedded value set founded on safety, reliability, sustainability, usability, serviceability, aesthetics and ethics.
	5. Process-oriented	Hypothesis and needs driven curiosity, evidence based creativity, logical and critical thinking.
Personal mind-set	4. Self-instruction	Curiosity, self-reflection, need-awareness, resourcefulness, competence-oriented, metacognition.
	3. Self-governance	Vision, self-consciousness, receptiveness, competence-oriented learner, priority-setting.
	2. Social attitude	Empathy, tolerance, reliability, moral and ethics.
	1. Self-efficacy	Initiative, decision-making and responsibility.

The elements have been enumerated by the chronological order in which these components typically enter the mind-set of an engineering student, and represent increasing levels of *qualification element complexity*. The *process complexity* of mind-set development is measured by Bloom's taxonomy for the affective domain (Figure 1). Tacit, but strategic enforcement and monitoring is required to obtain a satisfactory development in all students. The top three mind-set levels (Self-instruction, Process-oriented and Product-oriented) must be integrated into courses in an explicit manner.

2.4 –To interact

The third category, - *To interact*, includes communication and teamwork. *Table 6* describes elements of oral and written communication in order of increasing element complexity.

Table 6. Qualification elements of communication

Element complexity	Element description
5. Context analysis	Define communication objectives and analyse receiver competency.
4. Narrative style	Choose between multiple narrative styles in accord with context.
3. Quality control	Edit grammar, style, logic, clarity and sources.
2. Structure of content	Structure content according to standards.
1. Language and tool skills	Master language and information technology tools.

Table 7 describes elements of teamwork in order of increasing complexity.

Table 7. Qualification elements of teamwork

Element complexity	Element description
5. Development	Develop team processes as well as personal growth in the team members.
4. Monitoring	Monitor team processes and team members' adherence to defined codes.
3. Definition	Design time schedules and define codes of behaviour, efforts, ethics, and accountability.
2. Coordination	Coordinate tasks and resources.
1. Execution	Work in teams with individual tasks and adopt codes of behaviour, language, effort, deadlines, and accountability.

In order to embrace the qualification elements of communication and teamwork, engineering programmes must include courses with considerable time allocated to student-centred learning activities. At DTU, such programme elements are mandatory at the first, fourth, and sixth semester in the B. Sc. programme.

2.5 –To do

The qualification category, -*To do*, includes operative skills and problem solving. *Table 8* describes a taxonomy for operative skills based on work by Dave [7]. Dave's taxonomy is used here to express levels of training, from novice to expert, in both manual and cognitive tasks. When operative skills are not a prioritized teaching

objective, some students will remain novices throughout their study. Glaser's method of *Shaping* [8] can be used to train operative skills.

Table 8. Qualification elements of operative skills

Taxonomy levels	Level description
5. Naturalization	The expert can discriminate between situations and visualize solutions while diagnosing the task.
4. Articulate	Learners see the goal and adapt procedures.
3. Precision	Learners choose when and how to apply rules.
2. Manipulate	Understanding the context, the learner starts to recognize additional aspects and alternatives.
1. Imitate	Learners rely strongly on guidance and rules they have been instructed to follow.

Table 9 describes elements of problem solving in order of increasing *element complexity* based on work by Plant et al. [9]. The lowest level of complexity is the step-by-step execution of procedures following outlines. Operative skills are the main prerequisite for this level. It is for this reason we have chosen to combine operative skills and problem solving into one qualification category, *-to do*.

Table 9. Qualification elements of problem solving

Element complexity [9]	Element description [9]	Learning activity
5. Create	Design of procedures that are new to the problem solver.	Projects, capstone design, thesis work
4. Interpretation	Interpretation of problem description, identification of objective, translation of the real problem to an idealised problem, evaluation of validity of solution to idealized problem, prediction of impact of solution on problem sphere.	Case studies Course embedded mini projects
3. Strategy	The task of choosing the best suitable procedure among several valid procedures.	Case studies Course embedded mini projects
2. Diagnosis	The task of choosing between correct and incorrect procedures for a specific problem.	Textbook problems
1. Procedure	Operations to be done step-by-step by following a procedural outline. Ability relies on possession of operative skills.	Textbook problems

The elements of *Strategy* and *Interpretation* are rarely met in problem solving activities based solely on textbook problems, regardless of the level of the textbook. Case studies and mini projects embedded in courses are better options. Inclusion of these two elements in the qualification framework will help close the gap between problem solving at the introductory level and at the final level of an engineering programme.

3 SUMMARY

A proposal has been presented (*Table 2*) for a revised qualification framework at DTU. The set of qualifications are organized into logical categories: *-to know*, *-to be*, *-to interact*, *-to do*, and the elements in the qualification framework are easily integrated into outcome statements for individual courses. A number of taxonomies have been

associated with different categories of qualifications to facilitate instructional planning and execution in alignment with programme objectives. The proposed framework strengthens the focus on knowledge dimensions, on mind-set development and on operative skills. Finally, it embraces a method for designing problem solving activities to progressive levels of complexity.

In a companion paper [2], the elements of the proposed qualification framework are put into use to write Programme-Qualification Matrices for three different B. Sc. in Engineering programmes.

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